

Generation of Long Time Data Series for ESA heritage TPM missions

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The need for accessing historical Earth Observation (EO) data series strongly increased in the last ten years, particularly for long-term science and environmental monitoring applications. This trend is likely to increase even more in the future, in particular regarding the growing interest in global change monitoring which is driving users to request time-series of data spanning 20 years and more. The need to support the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) is also further driving demand for historical data series. The contents of EO data archives are continuously growing from a few years to decades and therefore, their value as a scientific time-series is ever-increasing. Hence, there is a strong need to preserve the EO space data without time constraints and to ensure that they are accessible and exploitable by the community. The preservation of EO space data can also be considered as a responsibility of the Space Agencies or data owners as they constitute a humankind asset. The Heritage Space Programme responds to the mandate of preserving, making accessible, and valorising ESA heritage space data and associated information holdings generated by payloads and instruments on-board space platforms from ESA and ESA-managed Third Party Missions with a strong focus on their accessibility and exploitability. Over 40 Earth Observation missions and 80 EO campaigns are initially included in the Heritage Space programme starting from 2023. As part of the programme activities, a particular focus is put on the generation of long time series of coherent data in support of climate change monitoring activities, needs and related applications. This paper describes the activities implemented at ESA for the generation of a long time series of data starting from the ESA Heritage Third Party Missions (TPM) L-band SAR instruments data holdings. These activities consisted of the recovery of data from old media, their consolidation, archiving, reprocessing and dissemination to end users.

Keywords: Third Party Missions; SAR; Data Preservation; Processes; Lifecycle; Data Valorisation, Earth Observation, Heritage Data Programme, Long Time Data Series, Fundamental Climate Data Record, ESA

Introduction

The ESA Heritage Space Programme responds to the mandate of preserving, making accessible, and valorising ESA heritage space data and associated information holdings generated by payloads and instruments on-board space platforms from ESA and ESA-managed Third Party Missions with a strong focus on their accessibility and exploitability. Over 40 Earth Observation missions and 80 EO campaigns are included in the Heritage Space programme.

Figure 1 – ESA and TPM Missions under Heritage Space Programme

As part of the programme activities, a particular focus is put on the recovery, reprocessing and the generation of long time series of coherent data in support of climate change monitoring activities, needs and related applications.

EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY (ESA) HERITAGE SPACE PROGRAMME

The Earth Observation part of the ESA Heritage Space Programme covers data from ESA missions and Third Party Missions (TPM) available at ESA through specific agreements nominally starting five years after the effective end of life of the mission or five years after end of the agreement (in case of the TPMs). The ESA Heritage Space Programme consists of four main streams of activities in Earth Observation:

1. Heritage Space ESA Inter-directorate Joint Activities
2. EO Heritage Space International Cooperation and Outreach
3. EO Space Data Preservation Systems and Services
4. EO Heritage Space Missions Discovery and Access
5. EO Heritage Space Missions Specific Activities (including data preservation, consolidation, valorisation and Fundamental Data Records)

The last two areas focus particularly on the ESA Historical Dataset rescuing, preservation and valorisation according to user communities' needs. The results of user consultations aimed at capturing and understanding Earth Science users' needs in terms of long-term preservation (including accessibility and exploitability aspects) has highlighted that the preservation of Earth Science data and associated knowledge is vital to support their research and application activities. The same need was also identified in the frame of discussions and cooperation ongoing between the Data Access and Preservation (DAP) Working Group European space members and ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) representatives and projects (<http://cci.esa.int/>).

Figure 2 – ESA International Cooperation Heritage Space Programme

The definitions of datasets composing the Fundamental Climate Data Records (FCDR) (i.e. processing levels and algorithms, formats, quality, orthorectification, etc.) have big impacts on the CCI projects' products and results and need to be clearly identified and documented.

LONG TIME DATA SERIES GENERATION

The management of ESA EO data holdings (including data from TPM's archived at ESA) is formally covered within the ESA Heritage Space Programme starting 5 years after their end of life (or end of ESA agreement).

The ESA involvement in the last 45 years on TPM missions could notably differ mission to mission, ranging from the full ground segment chain (task, acquire, process and data delivery) to only data delivery. For this reason, the holding could be quite different: for some missions we have from the raw data (i.e. satellite data stream) for other only the L1 processed data. Therefore, the Heritage activities could be very different mission by mission.

The following set of activities is being implemented in accordance with the LTDP Core standard documents (i.e. EO Data Preservation Guidelines Best Practices [1], EO Preserved Dataset Content (PDSC) [1], the Long Term Preservation of Earth Observation Space Data: Preservation Workflow [1]) defined in cooperation with international partners and organisations:

- Assessment of archived data and information holdings versus “Preserved DataSet Content Best Practice” [1] for all ESA and ESA managed TPMs.
- Consolidation of Level-0 (or Level-1 if Level-0 is not available) datasets (and associated information), and generation of two copies to be stored in two different locations.
- Ingestion in robotic tape libraries in the format of Open Archival Information System (OAIS) [5] standard Submission Information Packages (SIPs).
- Full datasets reprocessing, when feasible, for alignment with the most recent or future missions.
- Ensuring basic discoverability and dissemination through ESA standard systems.
- Progressive historical archives rationalisation.

As part of the above activities, a particular focus is put on the generation of long time series of coherent data in support of the Climate Change Initiative requirements and related applications.

LONG TIME DATA SERIES PROJECTS

ESA Copernicus Sentinel missions, along with the Copernicus Contributing Missions as well as Earth Explorers and Third Party missions are providing routine monitoring of our environment at the global scale, thereby delivering an unprecedented amount of data, and also posing a major challenge to achieving the full potential in terms of data exploitation. The emergence of large volumes of data (Petabytes era) raises new issues in terms of discovery, access, exploitation, and visualisation of data, with profound implications on how users do “data-intensive” Earth Science. In line with LTDP framework guidelines [1] for the preservation of long time series and to foster the exploitation of the dataset with the new emerging technology for big data analysis and reprocessing, various projects were started by the Agency, described in detail hereinafter.

SEASAT Recovery and Reprocessing

The satellite was launched in 1978 by NASA’s Jet Propulsion Laboratory, and was the first satellite designed for remote sensing of the Earth’s oceans with the first Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) onboard. Its data over Europe were acquired by the European Space Agency in the Oakhanger-UK station. The activity started with the recovery of the complete Seasat-SAR data holdings available at ESA and acquired during the short operational time span of the mission (August to October 1978). During its brief lifetime of just over 100 days, the satellite acquired information on ocean phenomena, such as surface and internal waves, currents and sea-surface winds for the study of ocean circulation. It also captured imagery of glaciers, sea ice, coastal regions, volcanoes, forests and land cover. These data (all Level-0 acquired over Europe and a few higher-level products) were migrated in the past years from old technology media to new ones and were stored, together with some supporting documentation, at ESA-ESRIN (Italy) and at Deutsches Zentrum für Luft-und Raumfahrt (DLR). In the framework of this activity, the information necessary to understand and use the Seasat-SAR data was recovered.

Figure 3 – ESA’s Seasat data holdings coverage

The information on SAR data format has allowed the Level-0 data to be read again and the visualisation of the available higher-level products through proper configuration of commercial tools. The following steps consisted of the definition of a consolidation procedure for the SAR dataset, in the inventorying and consolidation of the full dataset and of the associated documentation paving the way for any possible future exploitation. Due to the unavailability of the original data processor and therefore, the impossibility of re-processing Level-0 data, the Level-1 recovered products were finally used in a pilot application exercise for glaciers monitoring over Greenland in combination with data from ERS-2 mission to demonstrate the achievements and usefulness of this recovery exercise. The project was the first practical exercise of historical Earth Observation space-borne dataset recovery based on the application of the LTDP Guidelines [1] and provided as such also a valuable contribution for their consolidation and improvement.

Comparing data from three generations of radar missions – Seasat, ERS and Sentinel-1 – the retreat of two large glaciers in southeast Greenland over a 36-year period is evident in figure 4 below.

This preliminary analysis shows that the effects of climate change on the world's second largest ice sheet have had a major impact over the past three decades. The glaciers show significant retreat, with the upper glacier receding by about 5.5 km over the past 36 years. This melt is contributing to sea-level rise and the release of more freshwater into the North Atlantic.

Figure 4 – Greenland glaciers seen by three generations of radar missions

JERS-1/SEASAT/ALOS – L-BAND RADAR

The importance of L-band radar has been analysed in M. Ottinger and C. Kuenzer, 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12142228>), L-band SAR is particularly useful for geoscientific research on wetland and forest change mapping. The capability to penetrate canopy with long radar wavelength (L-band SAR) has been widely applied and investigated for mapping and monitoring of flooded vegetation, the retrieval of aboveground biomass, and the estimation of soil moisture and coastal area monitoring. Human activities and climate change-induced impacts are currently causing land degradation, deforestation and land use change. Long term data series are very important to address research into ecosystems sustainability and land modification climate-change-related, both in the past decades, in current days with SAR L-Band satellites such as the SAOCOM-1 constellation (Argentina's space agency CONAE) and in the future with the proposed ESA's ROSE-L.

The recovery and consolidation of the SEASAT SAR heritage mission dataset available at ESA has been aligned with JERS-1 L-Band SAR and ALOS PALSAR missions data in terms of processing chain and output format. As a result of these activities, the complete SEASAT and JERS-1 SAR datasets have been reprocessed and aligned to the more recent ALOS PALSAR dataset producing a long time series of coherent data spanning from 1978 to 2011 (with gaps between the three missions operational lifetime). These SAR data are now accessible on an open and free basis for all users through ESA.

JERS-1, launched in 1992 by JAXA, carried on-board an L-band HH polarization SAR instrument and an optical VNIR/SWIR one (unfortunately the SWIR broke at the beginning of the operations) up to 1998. ESA acquired, process and disseminate (during the satellite lifetime through a commercial partner, now directly) JERS-1 data in Tromsø (N) and Fucino (I) ground stations.

JERS-1 optical instrument (OPS) had 4 Bands, 3 looking at nadir and the 4th one (same wavelength of the 3rd) with off-nadir viewing (15.33 forward in-flight direction) allowing to make stereo pairs (an effective **two-line** stereoscopic along-track imaging capability). The stereo images are useful for geomorphology and digital elevation model (DEM) construction. These data are accessible as well on an open and free basis for all users through ESA.

ALOS-1 (aka Daichi), launched in 2006 by JAXA, carried on board a polarimetric L-band SAR (PALSAR) instrument and 2 optical instruments: PRISM (Panchromatic Remote-sensing Instrument for Stereo Mapping) with 2.5m resolution and AVNIR-2 (Advanced Visible and Near-Infrared Radiometer 2, and evolution of the sensor that was present on ADEOS) with 4 bands at 10m. The mission ended in 2011. PRISM data was really high resolution at the time being and today is often used in order to verify the geometry of other satellites of the period. PALSAR and AVNIR-2 data are accessible on free basis (a simple registration is needed) for all non-commercial users through ESA. PRISM data are accessible as well, but quota mechanism is in place (still considered valuable by Japan).

LANDSAT Long Time Data Series

USGS (United States Geological Survey) Landsat satellites' series are the world's longest running system of satellites for optical remote sensing of land, coastal areas, and shallow waters. ESA's data acquisitions, started in 1975, were part of an international agreement to get, to store and to distribute data over Europe and Africa sectors. The ESA Landsat dataset is a unique heritage to maintain and valorise for its peculiarity and historical value. Landsat satellites hosted onboard different types of optical medium-resolution sensors, evolved with the evolution of the satellite and technical evolutions, starting with MSS (MultiSpectral Scanner) instrument with only 4 bands in the VIS-NIR, going through TM (Thematic Mapper) and ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus), arriving now to the updated OLI-TIRS (Operational Land Imager - Thermal Infrared Sensor) with 9 band in VIS-NIR-SWIR and also two band in the Thermal Infrared.

The objectives of the Landsat Series are to:

- Image repetitively Earth's land and coastal areas with the aim of monitoring changes to those areas over time.
- Provide moderate-resolution optical remote sensing for land, coastal areas and shallow waters.
- Provide Earth observation data to support work in agriculture, geology, forestry, education, mapping, emergency response and disaster relief, as well as providing a long-term record of natural and human-induced changes to the Earth.

The programme opened entirely new fields of research, providing insights into geologic, agricultural, and land-use surveys, eventually leading to new paths of resource exploration - in all, for a better understanding of our planet's system. The success of the Landsat programme stimulated new approaches to data analysis and gave impetus to new sensor designs: for instance, the Copernicus Sentinel-2 sensor was designed in order to keep full compatibility with this fundamental dataset and expand it in terms of spatial and frequency resolutions.

Figure 5 – Landsat Data: retreating glacier evidence

From 1975, ESA began with its own ground systems, to acquire, process and archive data from Landsat, under the Earthnet program. Starting with a single satellite ground station, located in Fucino (Italy), the acquisition capability was increased in the following years with Kiruna (Sweden – operating April to October), Maspalomas (Canary Islands – Spain – operating on campaigns), Matera (Italy) and

Neustrelitz (Germany –Landsat 7 only) plus Landsat 5 data acquired with DLR portable station (Bishkek, Chetumal and Libreville). At the time being the satellites did not have a recorder on board, therefore the data could be taken only during the visibility of a ground station. The resulting dataset of the seven Landsat satellites, with over 1.8 million scenes, is now fully available under the Heritage Space Programme as open and free. As part of the International Ground Station (IGS) community, ESA is continuously maintaining efforts to distribute new Landsat 8 data under Earthnet's Third Party Missions. ESA's 45 years' worth of Landsat historical data observed over Continental Europe, African regions and the Arctic has become massive. Major efforts have been undertaken to improve processing and then produce the most up to date Level-1 products for the community. The Multi Spectral Scanner (MSS) instrument on board the Landsat 1 to 5 satellites was built by SBRC (Santa Barbara Research Center) of Hughes Aircraft Company in Goleta, CA.

In the context of the Landsat archive reprocessing, major improvements have been conducted regarding the MSS geometric processing. The product generation system of MSS has been aligned to the TM and ETM+ ones. The MSS telemetry is generally affected by missing and corrupted data, mainly because of mission ageing and archive degradation, resulting in a poor quality geometric model. The orbit, attitude and data from the Payload Control Data (PCD) stream are generally used to compute the geometric model. To overcome corrupted data issues, satellite position bias and attitude angle corrections are estimated as part of the geometric model refinement process, using the Ground Control Points (GCP) originating from the NASA GLS2000 dataset (<http://glcf.umd.edu/data/gls/>) for which the geolocation accuracy is estimated to be 25 m (RMSE). The geometric model is, then, calibrated by using information obtained over the complete orbit and not a single WRS (Word Reference System) scene. Hence, block adjustment techniques have been implemented to estimate an accurate georeferencing model and in order to perform subsequent ortho-rectification [2].

MOS-1 and MOS-1b

Multispectral Electronic Self-Scanning Radiometer (MESSR) and Visible and Thermal Infrared Radiometer (VTIR) products from the National Space Development Agency of Japan (NASDA) Marine Observation Satellites (MOS-1 and -1b) were received by the European Space Agency (ESA) during the 1980s and 90s.

MESSR is like the data from the USGS Landsat missions with a swath width of 100 km, 50 m spatial resolution and four multispectral bands in the blue, green, red and Near InfraRed (NIR).

VTIR is like the data from the NOAA AVHRR missions with a 500 km swath width, visible band at 900 m resolution and three NIR to thermal IR bands at 1.1 km resolution.

The first-ever full processing of ESA MOS-1/1b MESSR (Multispectral Electronic Self-Scanning Radiometer) and VTIR (Visible and Thermal Infrared Radiometer) data holdings into Level-1 products in EO-SIP packaging format has been completed and data has been successfully quality controlled with very good results in comparison to Landsat-5 TM radiometry. Both datasets have a limited radiometric correction, with Digital Numbers (DNs) generated. So, the Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) undertook a preliminary cross-comparison of the MESSR to Landsat-5 Thematic Mapper data to see if a conversion to radiometric units is possible. The results were promising, however, further work is ongoing to understand if the required ancillary data is available and can be extracted from the ESA archive.

Figure 6 – MOS-1 MESSR scenes acquisition over Gibraltar Strait and Guadalquivir estuary (visible a little plume from the river) on 19 June 1990.

An issue with the ESA Time Correlation files (which allow to correctly geolocate the data) in the period July 1992 - September 1993 did prevent the production of the data. New corrected Time Correlation (TC) files were generated, comparing the data in the telemetry and those in the Level 0 files, which allowed the processing and completing of the production of the data in this specific interval. Data will be made accessible on a free of charge and open basis for all users by Q2 2023.

AVHRR timeline

Data of the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) onboard many National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) satellites – and since 2006 on EUMETSAT MetOp-satellites, is the only source to provide long time series based on an almost unchanged sensor of the last 40 years with daily availability and 1.1 km spatial resolution.

This long period fulfils the requirements of the World Meteorological Organization for a statistical sound analysis to study climate change induced shifts of Essential Climate Variables (ECV). Beside the central NOAA, CLASS archive exists many local archives, which are partly not accessible or the data holdings are not well maintained to be used by research teams. A few archives in Europe have data holdings covering Europe on a daily basis but are not homogenised and consolidated. In the frame of ESA Heritage Space Programme the data holdings of University of Bern (Switzerland), European Space Agency, and Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (UK) are combined, redundancy removed, and validated to proof readability of the AVHRR LAC (1 km resolution) level 1b data. In a final step, metafiles and quick looks are generated to be included in a data container (SIP). The metafiles include some quality indicators to guarantee the usability of the dataset. This may help the user to select the needed files for their own investigations. Finally, the homogenised dataset was transferred to ESA to keep the unique AVHRR images alive for the next +50 years and make it accessible for all interested parties via ESA web interfaces.

The four to six band multi-spectral AVHRR data constitute a valuable data source for deriving time series of surface parameters, such as snow cover, land surface temperature or vegetation indices for monitoring global change. AVHRR data are residing in various archives worldwide, including several ESA facilities. The AVHRR Curation project aims at consolidating the AVHRR ESA Level 0 data holdings and at defining the technical approaches and solutions for the possible generation of a coherent European AVHRR dataset consisting of the combination of datasets from different organisations.

Figure – 8 European 1-km AVHRR archive hosted at ESA

In this context, an AVHRR Level 0 dataset consolidation procedure was defined in coordination with AVHRR data users and experts, to ensure consistency and homogeneity of the datasets.

The project has outlined the importance of assuring that the long-term series datasets are:

- homogeneous (data gap consolidation procedure shall be in place during operations or at mission end);
- consistent (inter-sensor consistency is one of the main requirements from the user community using long-term data series, i.e. to preserve the data and the knowledge of the family of sensor consistency and evolution and cross-validation assessment within the same family of sensors as AVHRR);
- include the measure of the uncertainty (it is of utmost importance to foster practices for sensor degradation measurement and preserve the measure of uncertainty in the product w.r.t the original mission requirements, quality performances expectation, and to keep track of sensor performance degradation).

The whole process for consolidation of the AVHRR data was in-line with the recommendations of the CEOS Working Group on Information Systems and Services (WGISS) to fulfil the needs for data management and stewardship maturity [1].

Conclusions

The emergence of large volumes of data raises new issues in terms of discovery, access, exploitation, and visualisation of data, with profound implications on how users do “data-intensive” Earth Science. In line with LTDP framework guidelines and strategy for the preservation of long time series and to foster the exploitation of the dataset with the new emerging technology for big data analysis and reprocessing, various projects were started by the Agency. These projects have outlined the importance of assuring that long-term series datasets are: homogeneous (data gap consolidation procedure shall be in place during operations or at mission end); consistent and include not only measure of the uncertainty (inter-sensor performance degradation) but also all ancillary data, like telemetry are not lost, and have demonstrated that data and/or metadata must be broken out of silos in order to be mined, proximity of data to the streaming processing chain and data locality is vital for cross-fertilisation and discovery of new products and services to the EO community.

REFERENCES

[1] CEOS WGISS Preservation Guidelines and Best Practices - <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/preservation/>

[2] [LANDSAT Products Description Document](#) - IDEAS-VEG-SRV-REP-1320 v.6.0